

2. Effect on YSB larval populations in 1987 WS of small changes in development rate (a), immigration rate (b), and oviposition rate (c).

semisymmetrical (Fig. 2c); a 20% alteration brought about the same amount of absolute changes in the first peak density but resulted in a higher increase (45.7%) in the second.

SIMYSB has been designed for application in YSB management. The user or researcher may choose to investigate single or combined common pest control tactics. Novel control strategies examined using the computer may lead to the design of useful field experiments. □

Life cycle of *Micraspis* sp. on brown planthopper (BPH) and rice pollen

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The coccinellid *Micraspis crocea* (Mulsant) feeds on plants and on leafhoppers and other small insect pests of rice. It also has been observed feeding on rice flower pollen. Beetles are

abundant in ricefields and could help suppress populations of several insect pests.

But because they feed on pollen, many farmers consider them a pest and often spray insecticides to control them.

We studied *M. crocea* in the greenhouse, using the BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and flowering rice panicles. Adult beetles collected from fields were caged on TN1 rice plants with BPH nymphs. Beetle eggs collected daily were placed in petri dishes lined with moist filter paper to determine incubation time. Individual larvae were placed in 2- × 20-cm glass vials with rice stems and second- and third-instar BPH. We reared 75 larvae using this procedure.

Another set of 75 larvae were reared in vials containing flowering rice panicles. Panicles and BPH were changed daily. Ladybeetle larvae were observed to determine time between stages, pupation period, and emergence of adults. Newly emerged adults were reared on both rice panicles and BPH to

Simulated yellow stem borer (YSB) population dynamics: modeling and evaluation

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A simulation model of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* population dynamics (SIMYSB) was constructed using the state variable approach and boxcar train technique.

YSB population dynamics in a farmer's field were compared to model output for 1987 wet season (WS) and 1988 dry season (DS). A 2,500-m² field in Calauan, Laguna, Philippines, was transplanted with C168 (local long-duration variety susceptible to YSB) and not treated with insecticides. The field was subdivided into 50 plots.

Weekly pest sampling started shortly after transplanting. Each week, all plants in three plots selected at random were examined for adult moths and egg masses; 25% of the plants were sampled for dissection.

Biology of *Micraspis* sp. on BPH nymphs and flowering panicles. IRRI greenhouse, 1988.

Stage	Developmental period on ^a (d)	
	BPH nymphs	Flowering panicles
Incubation period	4.0 ± 0	4.0 ± 0
1st instar	3.2 ± 0.07	3.35 ± 0.08
2d instar	3.4 ± 0.11	3.3 ± 0.15
3d instar	4.2 ± 0.17	4.4 ± 0.18
4th instar	4.4 ± 0.14	7.1 ± 0.24
Pupal stage	4.0 ± 0	4.0 ± 0
Egg to adult	23.1 ± 0.33	26.1 ± 0.38
Adult longevity	94.4 ± 4.41	74.47 ± 3.57

^aMean of 75 insects ± standard error.

determine longevity.

In general, *Micraspis* sp. survived and developed successfully on both pollen and BPH (see table). This could explain why this beetle is so abundant during rice flowering and during BPH outbreaks. More detailed studies are underway to determine the effects of rice pollen feeding.

1. Simulated and farmer's field YSB egg, larval, and pupal populations, Calauan, Philippines, 1987 WS. First-instar larvae were excluded.

2. Simulated and farmer's field YSB egg, larval, and pupal populations. Calauan, Philippines, 1988 DS. First-instar larvae were excluded.

Over a period of 105 d, the model satisfactorily simulated the time of all population density peaks, except one in 1987 WS (Fig. 1) and two in 1988 DS (Fig. 2). The failure to predict by 1 wk the second egg density peak for 1987 WS (Fig. 1) is attributed to sampling error. The failure to predict by 1 wk the second egg and first larval density peaks for 1988 DS (Fig. 2) is probably because low relative humidity in DS slowed insect development. The 1987 WS had two distinct generations in the field; population sizes in the first were much larger than in the second. The 1988 DS had one large, complete first and one small, incomplete second generation.

On the whole, the model simulated YSB field population dynamics well. The acceptable agreement between simulated and observed patterns of YSB population fluctuations allows use of the model for sensitivity analysis, research planning, and evaluation of pest control measures.

Source code with full documentation is available from IRRI. □

Life history and hosts of *Sogatodes pusanus* (Distant) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae)

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In ricefields, *S. pusanus* is often confused with whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* (Horváth). *S. pusanus* is not a rice pest but an *Echinochloa*-feeding planthopper. A colony of 100 adults can hopperburn a plant with 10 tillers in 5-7 d.

The planthoppers differ in color of body, apical cells of the fore wings, and shape of parameres. The two species can be identified by the following key:

yellow medially and dark brown laterally; apical cells of fore wing crescently dark brown; male parameres straight with two divergent processes apically

Sogatodes pusanus (Distant)
Pronotum uniformly whitish-yellow except dark brown or pale yellow

area underneath eyes; mesonotum whitish-yellow medially with dark brown outer sides of lateral carinae; fore wings with black pterostigma; male parameres broad basally and apically bifurcated without large spine

Sogatella furcifera (Horvath)

We studied the development of *S. pusanus* on 15 common ricefield plant species in three families—Poaceae (9), Cyperaceae (5), and Sphenocleaceae (1). Individual host plants were caged in 10 × 72-cm mylar cylinders (10 cm diam, 72 cm high) with side and top vents.

Five pairs of newly emerged adults were released per cage for oviposition. Host suitability was determined by measuring biological parameters: survival, growth index, fecundity, and life cycle duration.

S. pusanus completed development on only two plant species, *Echinochloa colona* and *E. crus-galli* (see table).

On *E. colona*, development from egg to adult took 19.7 ± 0.6 d with an incubation period of 7.5 ± 0.5 d;

Hosts of *Sogatodes pusanus*.^a IRRI greenhouse, Feb 1988.

Plant species	Eggs laid (no./5 females)	Egg hatchability ^b (%)	Nymph survival ^c	Growth index ^d
Poaceae				
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	245.7 ± 86.6 a	80.1 ± 9.9 a	87.5 ± 4.9 a	5.7 ± 0.8 a
<i>E. crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	138.2 ± 61.9 b	76.2 ± 9.1 b	83.7 ± 3.6 a	5.1 ± 0.6 a
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> Berg.	44.7 ± 36.4 c	0	0	0
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	26.2 ± 17.7 d	0	0	0
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L.	25.5 ± 23.3 d	0	0	0
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	23.5 ± 9.7 d	0	0	0
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	23.0 ± 2.1 d	0	0	0
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf	11.7 ± 7.9 d	0	0	0
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	11.2 ± 9.2 d	0	0	0
Cyperaceae				
<i>Cyperus brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	9.0 ± 3.6 d	0	0	0
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	7.4 ± 3.0 d	0	0	0
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	4.0 ± 1.6 d	0	0	0
<i>C. kyllingia</i> Endl.	3.2 ± 2.7 d	0	0	0
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	2.8 ± 1.5 d	0	0	0
Sphenocleaceae				
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	16.3 ± 13.6 d	0	0	0

^aMeans (X ± SD) followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

^bEgg hatchability (%) = $\frac{\text{eggs hatched (no.)}}{\text{eggs laid (no.)}} \times 100$

^cNymphal survival (%) = $\frac{\text{nymphs becoming adults (no.)}}{\text{eggs hatched (no.)}} \times 100$

^dGrowth index = $\frac{\% \text{ nymphs becoming adults}}{\text{mean development period (d)}}$